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for
EurEau

About P2GreenN

P2GreenN's ambition is to foster the paradigm shift in our current linearly organised urban blue infrastructure and agricultural nutrient management towards circular clean tech value chains that reduce N and P emissions. P2GreenN aims to develop innovative circular nutrient management systems that

- use wastewater and human urine and faeces from urban areas as a valuable resource,
- recycling N and P via four innovative clean technologies in three pilot regions into bio-based fertilisers,
- which are used for food production in agriculture across Europe, reducing dependencies on current mineral fertilisers.

P2GreenN's technologies can contribute to the net zero target of the Wastewater Framework Directive by recovering nutrients as local fertilisers.

Funded by
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P2GreeNs technology for recycling nutrients from human excreta are safe to use, proven in practice and continuously scientifically monitored.

P2GreeNs solutions will create a circular nutrient economy and decrease the energy and areal footprint of centralized sanitation systems, while increasing the availability of freshwater resources for other purposes (e.g. households).

The current legal framework needs revision to develop and scale up of more sustainable and circular solutions.

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Policy Brief

